

Resources and Methods for Bangla Regional Dialects: A Literature Review of Recent Corpora and Models

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Abstract—Bangla has a rich landscape of regional dialects that differ from the standard variety in vocabulary, phonology, and syntax. These dialects are widely used in daily communication yet remain underrepresented in natural language processing. In recent years several research groups have released datasets and baseline models that target translation between regional dialects and standard Bangla, automatic dialect identification, and named entity recognition for dialectal text. This review synthesizes these contributions and examines how they define tasks, collect data, design annotations, and evaluate systems. The discussion is organized around thematic clusters that include parallel corpora for dialect to standard translation, merged corpora for multi dialect analysis, regional named entity recognition resources, and curated datasets with multilingual alignment. Methodological trends such as reliance on social media text, use of native speaker validation, and the growing role of transformer based models receive particular attention. The review also highlights open challenges such as incomplete dialect coverage, data imbalance, lack of speech and sociolinguistic metadata, and limited integration with large language models. Finally, it outlines research gaps and future directions for more inclusive and robust Bangla dialect technologies.

Index Terms—Bangla language, Regional Bangla dialects, Dialect to standard Bangla translation, Neural machine translation, Low resource language processing, Dialect identification, Named entity recognition, Bangla dialect datasets, Multilingual benchmarks, Transformer based models, Sociolinguistics and dialect variation

I. INTRODUCTION

Bangla is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world and supports a large set of regional dialects that differ in phonology, lexicon, and sentence structure from the standard variety used in education and administration. [1], [2] These dialects shape identity and daily communication in many parts of Bangladesh but receive limited attention in mainstream natural language processing tools. Many existing Bangla systems assume standard written input and therefore struggle when users write in dialectal forms on social media, in local news, or in conversational applications. [3], [4]

Several recent works address this gap by creating datasets and models that focus on Bangla regional dialects. One prominent line of work introduces large parallel corpora that align

sentences from dialects such as Chittagong, Noakhali, Sylhet, Barishal, Mymensingh, and others with their equivalents in standard Bangla, and often with English translations as well. [1], [3], [5]–[7] Another direction constructs merged corpora that combine several existing resources into a unified benchmark for dialect identification and analysis. [2] A third set of studies targets named entity recognition in regional text and introduces the first benchmark for Bangla regional NER. [4] Alongside these corpora, some works also propose specialized neural architectures for dialect translation and region detection. [1]

This literature review has three main objectives. First, it maps the landscape of recent corpora for Bangla regional dialects and clarifies how they differ in scope, design, and intended use. Second, it compares methodological choices across works, including data sources, annotation workflows, model families, and evaluation metrics. Third, it offers a critical synthesis of strengths and limitations and identifies open research gaps that can guide future work on Bangla dialect technologies.

The review focuses on eight primary contributions. These include the Vashantor benchmark for dialect to Bangla translation and region detection, [1] the ONUBAD dataset for three dialects, [3] corpora dedicated to the Chittagonian and Sylheti dialects, [5], [8] two multi regional datasets that cover additional areas such as Rajshahi, Rangpur, Narail, and Khulna, [6], [7] the BanglaDial merged corpus, [2] and the ANCHOLIK NER benchmark for regional named entity recognition. [4] Together these works define the current state of resources and methods for Bangla regional dialect processing.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces background concepts and traces the evolution of regional resources in Bangla. Section III presents a thematic review of the corpora and models. Section IV analyzes methodological approaches in data collection, annotation, and modeling. Section V provides a critical discussion of research gaps. Section VI concludes with key insights and future directions.

II. BACKGROUND AND FOUNDATIONAL CONCEPTS

Bangla dialects vary across districts and divisions and influence both spoken and written communication in informal settings. [1], [2], [6] Many speakers write dialectal Bangla using the standard script, but their spelling choices often reflect local pronunciation and style rather than codified orthography. Standard Bangla tends to dominate textbooks, news media, and official documents, while dialects appear more frequently in social media posts, comments, and dialogues in local drama or film. [3], [5], [8] This pattern motivates resources that capture dialectal usage in channels where speakers naturally express themselves.

The corpora under review focus on three main task families. The first family covers dialect to standard translation, where the goal is to map sentences from a regional dialect into standard Bangla, sometimes with English translations for cross lingual work. [1], [3], [5]–[7] The second family addresses dialect identification, where a classifier predicts the region label for a given text segment. [1], [2], [7] The third family targets sequence labeling tasks such as named entity recognition, where each token receives a tag that indicates its entity type. [4]

Early work on dialect resources often focused on small parallel corpora for a single regional variety. For example, ChatgaiyyaAlap compiles aligned sentences for the Chittagonian dialect, while another dataset centers on Sylheti. [5], [8] These efforts showed that dialects diverge from standard Bangla not only in vocabulary but also in preferred sentence patterns and negative constructions. Later works extended this idea to multiple dialects and introduced larger benchmarks with consistent annotation and evaluation protocols. Vashantor and ONUBAD illustrate this step, while BanglaDial and BanglaRegionalTextCorpus show how multiple corpora can be merged or curated to capture broader regional diversity. [1]–[3], [7]

From a modeling perspective, recent datasets align with broader trends toward transformer based architectures in natural language processing. Several works fine tune multilingual or Bangla specific transformer models such as mT5, BanglaT5, mBERT, and BanglaBERT for translation or classification tasks. [1], [4] Others still explore recurrent neural networks for low resource translation tasks, especially where dataset sizes are modest. [5] Across these works evaluation relies on established metrics such as BLEU, METEOR, ROUGE, character and word error rate, and F1 scores for classification and NER.

Overall, the current generation of Bangla regional resources emerges at the intersection of dialectology, corpus construction, and modern neural modeling. They build on earlier efforts in Bangla NER, machine translation, and text classification for standard language, but extend coverage into regional varieties and social media style text. [1], [4] This review positions each dataset within that broader trajectory and examines how well they support the development of inclusive language technology.

III. THEMATIC REVIEW

A. *Parallel Corpora for Dialect to Standard Translation*

A central theme in recent work is the construction of parallel corpora that link regional dialects to standard Bangla at sentence level. These resources enable neural machine translation systems that can normalize dialectal input and also support downstream tasks such as sentiment analysis and entity recognition in regional text. [1], [3], [5]

Vashantor is one of the largest and most comprehensive benchmarks in this space. [1] It provides 32 500 samples that cover standard Bangla, Banglish, English, five regional Bangla dialects, and their Banglish variants. The dialectal part focuses on Chittagong, Noakhali, Sylhet, Barishal, and Mymensingh, with each region represented by both Bangla script and Banglish text. The dataset splits data into training, validation, and test sets and reports detailed statistics on corpus size, text length, and regional distribution. Human translators from each region follow explicit guidelines and the authors report high inter annotator agreement using Cohen’s and Fleiss’ kappa, which supports the reliability of the translations.

ONUBAD also targets dialect to standard translation but focuses on three regions, namely Chittagong, Sylhet, and Barisal. [3] It provides 1 540 words, 130 clauses, and 980 sentences per dialect, with standard Bangla and English translations. The dataset includes metadata about phonetic and grammatical features and is designed for both translation and dialect classification tasks. The authors highlight the role of professional dialect experts in validating the mappings and provide summary statistics on word length and sentence length distributions.

ChatgaiyyaAlap concentrates on Chittagonian and offers 4 012 aligned sentences between standard Bangla and this dialect, along with a dictionary of 1 500 word pairs. [8] The dictionary standardizes vocabulary choices and helps reduce ambiguity in translation. Data sources include social media posts, comments, and dialogues from online dramas. The creators invest substantial effort in manual cleaning, including removal of emojis, numbers, and inconsistent spacing, and rely on native speakers to refine both the dataset and the dictionary.

Another parallel corpus centers on the Sylheti dialect. Prama and Oni compile 5 002 sentence pairs along with clause and word level statistics, yielding 10 004 sentences when counting both Sylheti and standard Bangla sides. [5] The data comes from newspapers, social media, community contributions, and Sylheti drama dialogues. The authors emphasize the scarcity of written Sylheti materials and document the challenges of normalizing variable spellings. They position the corpus as a foundation for translation and other NLP tasks such as sentiment analysis and named entity recognition.

Two additional datasets extend the parallel approach to other regions. BD Dialect provides words and clauses for Standard Bangla, Noakhali, Sylhet, Chittagong, Rajshahi, and Mymensingh, with English translations for each entry. [6] Each CSV file contains 950 aligned rows, and the authors include preprocessing scripts and metadata in a public repository.

BanglaRegionalTextCorpus focuses on sentence level data for Rangpur, Barisal, Narail, and Khulna and aligns each regional sentence with its standard Bangla and English variants. [7] The corpus contains 4653 sentences, with careful balancing across regions and rigorous validation by native speakers.

Taken together these parallel corpora cover a growing number of Bangla dialects and provide a foundation for translation between regional varieties and the standard language. However, coverage remains incomplete, and corpora differ in size, domain, and alignment granularity. Vashantor and ONUBAD emphasize lexical and sentence diversity, while BD Dialect and BanglaRegionalTextCorpus aim for balanced, manually curated samples. ChatgaiyyaAlap and the Sylheti corpus dig deeper into a single dialect and provide richer contextual examples and auxiliary resources such as dictionaries.

B. Merged and Multi Dialect Corpora for Classification and Analysis

A second theme is the construction of merged corpora that integrate multiple datasets into unified resources for dialect identification and analysis. These corpora often expose natural class imbalance and are particularly useful for studying re-sampling, cost sensitive learning, and fairness in low resource NLP.

BanglaDial is a prominent example of such a merged dataset. [2] It aggregates sentence level text from four primary sources, namely Vashantor, ONUBAD, the REGIPA Bhashamul dataset, and a Bangla Dialect Dataset that contains several regional varieties. The final corpus includes 60729 sentences annotated with twelve classes that represent eleven dialects and standard Bangla. The authors provide detailed statistics on class distribution, average word counts, and average character counts per dialect. They document the merging process, including duplicate removal, normalization of dialect labels, and harmonization of preprocessing steps across sources.

BanglaDial stands out because it explicitly retains the natural imbalance of dialectal samples. Chittagong, Kishoreganj, and Narail contribute large numbers of sentences, while regions such as Rajshahi and Noakhali appear less often. [2] The authors compute imbalance indicators such as the proportion of sentences in the top three and top five classes, normalized Shannon entropy, and the imbalance ratio between the largest and smallest classes. They argue that this structure reflects real world data availability and offers a realistic testbed for research on imbalanced learning.

BanglaRegionalTextCorpus, although not a merged dataset in the same sense, also supports dialect classification and analysis. [7] The authors train LSTM, Bi LSTM, and Conv1D models to classify sentences into four regional classes and report accuracy and F1 scores for each region. Their results show that LSTM slightly outperforms the other architectures, while Bi LSTM offers more balanced performance across classes. They also provide lexical statistics, n gram frequency tables, and word clouds that illustrate regional differences in vocabulary and conversational patterns.

Vashantor contributes to this theme by including a dialect region detection task in addition to translation. [1] The authors fine tune mBERT, Bangla BERT base, and a customized DialectBanglaBERT model on region labeled data and report accuracy, log loss, and F1 scores for each dialect. Dialect-BanglaBERT achieves the best performance, especially in regions like Chittagong and Mymensingh, where subtle lexical and phonological cues matter. Confusion matrices and F1 score heatmaps reveal which dialect pairs are most often confused, and the authors relate these patterns to linguistic similarity measured via cosine similarity between speech corpora.

These multi dialect datasets and experiments highlight both the promise and the difficulty of automatic dialect identification. They show that transformer based models can capture many regional cues but also confirm that dialects with limited data or greater divergence from standard Bangla remain hard to classify. They also demonstrate the value of unified benchmarks such as BanglaDial for testing data balancing strategies and robust evaluation protocols.

C. Regional Named Entity Recognition

Named entity recognition in Bangla has a longer history in standard language settings, but regional dialects introduce new challenges due to spelling variation, informal style, and domain specific vocabulary. ANCHOLIK NER is the first benchmark that targets named entity recognition across several Bangla regional dialects. [4]

ANCHOLIK NER contains 17405 sentences and 101817 words annotated with ten entity tags across five regions, namely Barishal, Chittagong, Mymensingh, Noakhali, and Sylhet. [4] The dataset combines text from publicly available resources with manual translations and alignment of named entities across dialects. The authors design a tag set that covers persons, organizations, locations, relations, food, animals, roles, colors, and objects and adopt the BIO scheme. They also construct a hybrid translation dataset that aligns standard Bangla and regional dialect sentences, while preserving entity boundaries.

The study evaluates three transformer based models, namely BanglaBERT, Bangla BERT base, and multilingual BERT cased, under different training configurations and batch sizes. [4] BanglaBERT achieves the highest overall performance, with F1 scores above 80 for Mymensingh and Barishal and somewhat lower scores for Sylhet and Chittagong. The authors further introduce a weighted loss function to compensate for class imbalance among entity types and analyze entity wise F1 scores across dialects. Their results show that frequent categories such as location and relation perform well, while less frequent or more semantically diffuse types such as animal and role remain challenging.

A detailed error analysis reveals recurrent confusion patterns. For example, role is often misclassified as relation, and organization tends to collapse into location, especially in dialects with stronger divergence from standard Bangla. [4] The authors link these errors to both class imbalance and dialect specific lexical variation and argue for future work

on dialect aware tokenization and vocabulary extension. They also discuss how ANCHOLIK NER can support evaluation of large language models in low resource dialectal settings and encourage future research that integrates dialect resources with generative models.

Although ANCHOLIK NER is the only dedicated regional NER dataset among the works reviewed here, it connects to the parallel corpora and merged datasets in several ways. Parallel dialect to standard corpora can provide additional context for entity disambiguation and can support distant supervision by projecting entity labels from one variety to another. [1], [6] Merged corpora such as BanglaDial can offer unlabeled dialect text for pretraining or domain adaptation of NER models. [2] Future work can exploit these links more systematically.

D. Curated Multi Regional Resources with Multilingual Alignment

A final theme concerns curated datasets that balance coverage across regions and provide multilingual alignment with English. BanglaRegionalTextCorpus and BD Dialect are representative of this approach. [6], [7]

BD Dialect provides word and clause level alignments for Standard Bangla and five dialects, namely Noakhali, Sylhet, Chittagong, Rajshahi, and Mymensingh, along with English translations. [6] The dataset design emphasizes precise, parallel structure for each entry and includes both short units and longer clauses. Data collection relies on native speakers and regional literature, and the authors validate entries through multi annotator review. They also document the role of public domain literary sources and describe how they ensured copyright compliance.

BanglaRegionalTextCorpus focuses on four other regions and operates at sentence level. [7] The authors collect sentences from community interactions, field recordings, and digital sources and then align them with standard Bangla and English. They enforce a balanced distribution of sentences across regions and conduct rigorous validation with multiple native speakers per dialect. The paper reports detailed statistical analyses, including sentence length distributions, vocabulary sizes, n gram frequencies, and word clouds per region. It also demonstrates baseline dialect classification experiments with deep learning models.

These curated multi regional resources complement large scale benchmarks like Vashantor and merged corpora like BanglaDial. Their careful balancing and multilingual alignment support controlled experiments in dialect classification and translation, as well as cross linguistic studies that compare regional Bangla with English. [6], [7] They also highlight the value of close collaboration with communities and the importance of ethical data collection, including informed consent and anonymization.

IV. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES

A. Data Collection and Sampling Strategies

Across the reviewed works, data collection strategies reflect both practical constraints and specific research goals. Many

corpora draw heavily on social media platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, and Instagram. Examples include ONUBAD, ChatgaiyyaAlap, the Sylheti corpus, BanglaDial, and BanglaRegionalTextCorpus. [2], [3], [5], [7], [8] Social media offers rich dialectal content but also introduces noise, code switching, and varying spelling conventions.

Several datasets supplement social media with curated sources. Vashantor and BD Dialect incorporate newspaper text, regional literature, and transcribed spoken conversations to capture both formal and informal registers. [1], [6] BanglaRegionalTextCorpus collects sentences from on site fieldwork and community interactions, emphasizing natural conversational utterances. [7] The Sylheti corpus makes explicit use of oral histories, folklore, and drama dialogues to compensate for the scarcity of written materials. [5]

Sampling strategies vary. Some corpora aim for broad coverage and accept natural imbalance, as in BanglaDial and Vashantor. [1], [2] Others explicitly enforce balanced distributions across regions, such as BanglaRegionalTextCorpus and the regional slices within Vashantor’s training, validation, and test splits. [1], [7] The choice reflects trade offs between realism and controlled experimentation. Imbalanced corpora mirror real world frequency patterns but make evaluation more complex, while balanced corpora offer clean benchmarks but may underrepresent highly active dialect communities.

B. Annotation Workflows and Quality Control

Annotation workflows typically involve native speakers from each dialect region, often with linguistic training or relevant academic backgrounds. Vashantor employs multiple translators per region and uses double or triple annotation with consensus based resolution for difficult cases. [1] It quantifies agreement using Cohen’s and Fleiss’ kappa and reports high scores for regions such as Noakhali, Mymensingh, and Barishal, indicating strong consistency among annotators.

ONUBAD relies on regional dialect specialists for both data collection and validation and describes explicit guidelines for mapping dialectal sentences to standard Bangla. [3] ChatgaiyyaAlap uses five Chittagonian native speakers with expertise in standard Bangla to validate both sentence alignments and dictionary entries. [8] The Sylheti corpus stresses the role of community contributors and manual verification by native speakers to ensure both linguistic accuracy and cultural appropriateness. [5]

BD Dialect and BanglaRegionalTextCorpus adopt multi step validation pipelines with three native speakers per dialect who evaluate correctness, naturalness, and context. [6], [7] In cases of disagreement, annotators discuss and reach consensus, and unresolved items are removed from the final dataset. ANCHOLIK NER applies similar principles to entity annotation, where multiple annotators label sequences and disagreements are resolved through discussion and majority voting. [4]

Quality control also covers preprocessing choices. Most datasets remove duplicate entries, normalize Unicode, and strip emojis, user mentions, and hashtags. BanglaDial, ChatgaiyyaAlap, and ONUBAD describe these steps in detail

and show examples of raw versus cleaned text. [2], [3], [8] Some corpora, such as BanglaRegionalTextCorpus, carefully retain stop words to preserve contextual meaning, while others prioritize a leaner representation for model training. [7]

C. Model Architectures and Training Protocols

Model choices reflect both the size of datasets and broader trends in NLP. For translation tasks, Vashantor experiments with mT5, BanglaT5, and a customized DialectBanglaT5 model that adds an extra cross attention layer and gating mechanism to better handle dialectal variation. [1] DialectBanglaT5 shows consistent gains over the baselines across metrics such as character error rate, word error rate, BLEU, METEOR, and ROUGE, especially for challenging dialects like Chittagong. The authors also perform hyperparameter tuning for each dialect, adjusting learning rates, batch sizes, and numbers of training epochs.

The Sylheti corpus uses recurrent neural network models such as LSTM, GRU, BiLSTM, and BiGRU for translation, reflecting its moderate size and focus on sequence to sequence architectures. [5] ONUBAD suggests both sequence to sequence and transformer based models such as BanglaT5 for dialect translation and outlines how standard metrics can evaluate translation quality. [3]

For dialect identification, Vashantor fine tunes mBERT, Bangla BERT base, and DialectBanglaBERT, which adds an extra self attention layer above the final transformer block and uses mean pooling followed by a classification head. [1] DialectBanglaBERT achieves higher accuracy and F1 scores than the baselines and demonstrates improved robustness across dialects. BanglaRegionalTextCorpus tests LSTM, Bi LSTM, and Conv1D models with a shared embedding layer and fixed sequence length for sentence classification. [7] BanglaDial, while primarily a dataset paper, positions itself as a benchmark for future experiments with both classical and neural classifiers and emphasizes opportunities for research on imbalanced learning. [2]

In ANCHOLIK NER, the authors fine tune BanglaBERT, Bangla BERT base, and multilingual BERT for token level tagging. [4] They explore different batch sizes and numbers of epochs and also introduce a class weighted cross entropy loss to address entity imbalance. The study includes confusion matrices and entity wise F1 scores that highlight which categories and dialects remain difficult.

D. Evaluation Metrics and Analysis Practices

Evaluation metrics follow established standards in machine translation and sequence labeling. Translation work uses character error rate, word error rate, BLEU, METEOR, and ROUGE scores to capture different aspects of lexical and structural quality. [1], [3], [5] Vashantor presents metric wise improvements of DialectBanglaT5 over baselines for each dialect and provides visualizations such as bar charts and radar plots to illustrate gains. [1] The Sylheti study evaluates multiple n gram BLEU and ROUGE variants and discusses challenges in translating idiomatic expressions.

For classification tasks, accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and log loss are common metrics. [1], [2], [7] Vashantor reports region wise F1 scores and confusion matrices for mBERT, Bangla BERT base, and DialectBanglaBERT and analyzes which dialects are most often confused. [1] BanglaRegionalTextCorpus compares LSTM, Bi LSTM, and Conv1D across regions and shows that some dialects, such as Narail and Khulna, are more difficult to classify than others. [7]

ANCHOLIK NER relies on precision, recall, and F1 scores at entity level and examines both macro and micro averages. [4] The authors supplement numeric metrics with confusion matrices and per entity F1 tables to uncover systematic error patterns. They also connect performance differences to lexical overlap with standard Bangla and to degree of dialectal divergence.

Several datasets include broader statistical analyses such as sentence length distributions, vocabulary sizes, Zipf plots, and n gram frequency tables. [2], [6], [7] These analyses help characterize regional variation and provide context for modeling choices and error patterns. They also highlight the interplay between lexical diversity and classification difficulty.

V. CRITICAL ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH GAPS

The reviewed works represent important progress toward inclusive NLP for Bangla dialects, yet several limitations and open questions remain. A critical synthesis across themes reveals gaps in dialect coverage, modality, annotation depth, experimental design, and integration with broader language technology.

First, dialect coverage is still partial. Parallel corpora and classification datasets focus heavily on a core set of regions, such as Chittagong, Sylhet, Barishal, Noakhali, Mymensingh, Rangpur, Narail, and Khulna. [1]–[3], [6], [7] Many other dialects in Bangladesh remain unrepresented or appear only in small quantities. Even within covered regions, corpora mostly capture a single variety per district and do not account for micro regional variation or sociolects. This limits the generality of models and may bias systems toward more visible or better resourced dialect communities.

Second, most resources are text only and do not include aligned speech or phonetic annotations. BanglaDial and Vashantor provide rich written samples, but they do not offer audio recordings or prosodic features. [1], [2] BD Dialect mentions a small set of audio clips collected for internal verification, yet these are not aligned at scale. [6] As a result, current models cannot directly learn dialect specific pronunciation patterns or code switching in spoken language. This gap is notable because many dialect differences are phonological and may be difficult to capture purely from written approximations.

Third, annotation schemes focus mainly on direct linguistic mappings and do not include sociolinguistic metadata. Most datasets do not record speaker age, gender, education level, or socio economic background. [4], [6], [7] Without such information it is hard to study how dialect usage interacts with social factors or to design models that are sensitive to

demographic variation. Moreover, there is limited discussion of how power relations and language attitudes may influence data collection or annotation choices.

Fourth, experimental designs, while thorough in many respects, often evaluate models on the same domain and platform from which training data is drawn. For example, systems trained on social media text are mostly evaluated on similar posts and comments. [3], [5], [8] There is less emphasis on cross domain generalization, such as testing social media trained models on regional news articles or transcribed conversations. This limits understanding of how robust dialect models are to domain shift.

Fifth, integration with large language models remains limited. Some works mention future plans to use large models such as GPT or other instruction tuned systems for dialect translation, normalization, or emotion recognition. [1], [4] However, current experiments focus mainly on fine tuning medium sized transformers such as BanglaBERT and mBERT. As a result, we lack systematic studies of how large language models handle low resource dialects and how regional corpora can guide adaptation or instruction tuning.

Sixth, while several papers recognize data imbalance, there is still limited exploration of algorithmic strategies to mitigate it. BanglaDial explicitly frames imbalance as a research opportunity and computes quantitative indicators, but it does not include baseline resampling or cost sensitive models. [2] ANCHOLIK NER proposes a weighted loss for BanglaBERT, yet entity wise F1 scores show that rare categories remain challenging. [4] Future work could combine these datasets with methods such as focal loss, synthetic minority oversampling, or data augmentation tailored to dialectal text.

Seventh, parallel corpora are primarily used for translation and region detection, while their potential for cross task transfer remains underexplored. For instance, aligned dialect to standard sentences could support projection of entity labels or sentiment annotations, thus helping to bootstrap NER and sentiment models for dialects. [1], [6], [7] Similarly, dialect identification models could assist in domain adaptation by routing inputs to region specific translation or NER models. These directions require coordinated experimentation across datasets.

Finally, ethical discussions are present but could go deeper. Most works state that they anonymize social media data and obtain informed consent from volunteers, and some explain how they avoid copyrighted text or sensitive content. [3], [4], [6], [7] Few, however, engage with broader issues such as potential misuse of dialect identification for surveillance, reinforcement of stereotypes, or marginalization of less prestigious varieties. As dialect aware NLP becomes more capable, these questions will grow in importance.

Overall, the current landscape of Bangla dialect resources is promising but still fragmented. More comprehensive coverage, multimodal data, richer metadata, robust evaluation, and stronger ethical grounding would strengthen this area and support the development of inclusive, accountable language technologies.

VI. CONCLUSION

This literature review surveyed eight recent contributions that focus on Bangla regional dialects through the lenses of corpus creation and model development. The works collectively introduce large parallel corpora for dialect to standard translation, merged and curated datasets for dialect identification, and the first benchmark for regional named entity recognition. [1]–[8] They show that careful data collection with native speakers, explicit annotation guidelines, and rigorous preprocessing can yield reliable resources even in low resource settings. They also demonstrate that transformer based models, when adapted to dialectal data, can achieve strong performance on translation, classification, and NER tasks.

At the same time, the review identified several research gaps. Dialect coverage remains incomplete, speech and prosody are largely absent, and sociolinguistic metadata is rare. Models are seldom tested across domains, and integration with large language models is still at an early stage. Data imbalance and cross task transfer opportunities deserve more systematic attention. Ethical considerations, especially around fairness and potential misuse of dialect technology, call for deeper reflection.

Future work can build on the foundations laid by these corpora and models in several ways. Researchers can extend coverage to additional dialects and micro varieties, design multimodal datasets that include speech, and incorporate demographic information under strong privacy safeguards. They can explore joint modeling of translation, identification, and NER, supported by shared datasets and evaluation protocols. They can also investigate how large language models respond to dialectal prompts and how regional resources can guide safe and effective adaptation.

As Bangla speakers continue to use regional dialects across digital platforms, the need for dialect aware language technologies will grow. The resources and methods reviewed here provide an important starting point. With sustained collaboration among linguists, technologists, and communities, future work can move toward systems that respect and support the full diversity of Bangla language use.

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